

Motives, Fear of Cancer Recurrence, and Optimism Affecting Resilience and QoL in Breast Cancer Patients

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Cancer is a leading cause of death worldwide. Cancer patients may experience difficulties in making plans, fear of cancer recurrence, fear of the future, and a heightened sense of vulnerability. The present study examined whether motives, fear of cancer recurrence, optimism, and pessimism predict resilience and quality of life (QoL) among breast cancer patients. QoL was assessed in terms of psychological well-being and social well-being. A purposive sample of 240 breast cancer patients aged between 30 to 73 participated in the study. Participants were administered the unified motive scale, fear of cancer recurrence scale, life orientation scale, Bharathiar University resilience scale and quality of life-patient scale. Simple and multiple linear regression analyses were used for data analysis. Results indicated that intimacy and optimism positively predicted psychological well-being, while fear and fear of cancer recurrence negatively predicted psychological well-being. Additionally, the results revealed that intimacy and optimism positively predicted social well-being, while fear and fear of cancer recurrence negatively predicted social well-being. Power, achievement and intimacy along with optimism positively predicted resilience, while fear and fear of cancer recurrence negatively predicted resilience among breast cancer patients. The findings highlight the importance of psychological factors such as motives, fear of cancer and optimism in promoting resilience and quality of life. Understanding these factors can aid in developing targeted interventions to enhance psychological outcomes among breast cancer patients.

Keywords: Motives, fear, optimism, pessimism, resilience, quality of life, cancer

One of the main causes of death worldwide is cancer (Schmer et al., 2008). India will experience a 0.05 million (5.6%) annual average rise in the number of breast cancer patients between 2020 and 2030 (Pillai et al., 2024). The five most prevalent cancer sites are the

mouth, cervix uteri, tongue, breast, and lung (Mathur et al., 2020). There is increased attention devoted to the psychosocial effects of cancer as a result of advances in medical technology for cancer treatment, as well as more technologically advanced medications, which increase longevity in patients. Interest in personality study in health has been bolstered by advancements in fields such as behavioral medicine, health psychology, and psychosomatic medicine (Wiebe & Smith, 1997). One setting or instrument for advancing towards the achievement of the widely acknowledged objective of offering sufficient psychological treatment to everyone impacted by cancer, whether directly or indirectly, worldwide, is psycho-oncology (Kreitler, 2019). The discipline of psycho-oncology covers a diverse range of research and practice efforts that seek to ameliorate the psychological, social, and emotional sequelae following a person's diagnosis of cancer (Rankin et al., 2019).

Comprehending the motivations behind the behaviors and coping strategies of cancer patients is essential to delivering all-encompassing treatment and assistance. The unified motive scale provides a framework for analyzing these motives and has five unique subscales: the need for power, achievement, affiliation, intimacy and fear (Russell, 2004). One of the basic and important components of human society is power. According to Russell, "the primary motivation causing the changes that social science has to study is the love of power" (Russell, 2004). More severe physical disease and affective symptoms were reported by those with high power, inhibition, and power stress scores than by any other group of

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individuals, or in particular, by those with low power, inhibition and power stress scores. It appears that blocked power causes long-term sympathetic activation, which raises blood pressure and produces more adrenaline, which disrupts lymphocyte function and erodes the body's immune system's ability to fight infectious diseases. However, effective and rewarding power expression may improve adaptability (McClelland, 1982). Additionally, the drive for achievement plays a crucial role in shaping individuals' behavior and aspirations. The drive to achieve great outcomes by establishing lofty goals and working hard to reach them is known as the need for achievement (Murray, 1938). According to McClelland, achievement motivation is an individual's constant pursuit of excellence. Achievement-oriented people can see difficulties as doable situations rather than dwelling on unpleasant aspects. They will also have a strong sense of control over their surroundings (McClelland, 1961). Furthermore, the need for affiliation underscores the inherent human desire for social connection and belonging. The need for affiliation refers to creating, preserving, and mending healthy interpersonal relationships. Individuals with a high need for affiliation are outgoing, amiable, and eager to engage in social situations, and they prefer to be with other people than alone (Atkinson et al., 1954). The pursuit of intimacy, which emphasizes the value of intimate and personal interactions in people's lives, is equally significant. Intimacy refers to a persistent inclination or readiness to pursue experiences of intimate, close, and warm social connection (McAdams, 1980). Those driven by intimacy are liked by others and feel content and joyful in dyadic relationships and life in general (Weinberger et al., 2010). Finally, fear is a basic human motivation that frequently shapes choices and behaviors, especially when it comes to one's health and well-being. The fear (or avoidance) component causes one to avoid undesirable goal states and, if avoidance is effective, to experience fewer negative feelings (Schonbrodta et al., 2012).

It has been said that cancer patients and survivors live their entire lives fearing a recurrence of their disease. Fear of cancer recurrence means "the fear or worry that cancer will return or progress in the same organ or another part of the body." For individuals with breast, ovarian, colon, lung, or prostate cancer, fear of cancer recurrence is the first or second most frequently reported problem (Lebel et al., 2014). Low to moderate fear of cancer was reported by cancer survivors; this is regarded as one of the biggest issues and the most commonly acknowledged unmet requirements. Throughout the survivorship trajectory, the fear of cancer recurrence stays constant (Simard et al., 2013). Habitual optimism, an overall propensity to anticipate favorable results (Carver & Scheier, 2014) is linked to mortality, quality of life, and mental and physical health (Anthony et al., 2016). Studies have shown that optimism is associated with better quality of life (Finck et al., 2018; Schou-Bredal et al., 2017). In the context of breast cancer, optimism plays a crucial role in mental health and overall functioning (Colby & Shifren, 2013). Greater optimism and hope for the future help cancer survivors live with the disease better and even experience personal growth (Bozo et al., 2009). Also, low optimism is identified as one of the main factors contributing to patients' depressive symptoms getting worse (Kim & So, 2012). Pessimism can be described as the degree to which a person expects negative experiences in the future, which can predict an individual's stress behavior (Scheier & Carver, 1985). Compared to women with low optimism, those with greater optimism reported better social and mental functioning (Colby & Shifren, 2013).

Patients with pessimism generally had considerably poorer quality of life scores than those who were not (Peterson et al., 2008). Particularly during the course of breast cancer, women who exhibit a high degree of pessimism are more likely to have elevated levels of anxiety and despair, in addition to a decline in health-related quality of life. The findings suggest that avoiding pessimism may be more crucial than being positive (Zenger et al., 2011).

Cancer patients suffer from several symptoms that impact their quality of life. Higher mental distress, worse physical and social functioning, and a lower overall quality of life are linked to greater symptom loads (Heidrich et al., 2006). When the term "quality of life" first appeared in the context of cancer care in the 1980s, it was primarily used to refer to an individual's functional state and capacity to carry out everyday tasks (Berglund et al., 1991). With time, the idea expanded, and other components, including social, emotional, cognitive, and sexual functioning, were included in measuring quality of life. Besides widening the focus to include psychosocial aspects, it is also critical to refocus attention from factors that lower quality of life to factors that enhance it (Ristevska-Dimitrovska et al., 2015). Many studies have demonstrated a strong correlation between resilience levels and the overall quality of life (Ristevska-Dimitrovska et al., 2015). We can view resilience as a fundamental quality, a personality attribute that permits a person to preserve mental well-being in the face of challenging circumstances (Connor, 2006; Richardson, 2002). More resilient patients enjoy substantially higher quality of life in nearly every area (Ristevska-Dimitrovska et al., 2015). The psychosocial care component of resilience promotion impacts the well-being of patients and their families (Rosenberg et al., 2013).

Cancer patients endure a profound impact on their mental health and emotional well-being. This emotional toll can affect their overall quality of life and hinder their recovery process. The present study aims to find the variables that predict breast cancer patients' resilience and quality of life (psychological & social well-being). Understanding these facets will enable this study to provide information that will aid in developing interventions and support programs intended to enhance the resilience, psychological well-being and social well-being of breast cancer patients.

Method

Participants

A purposive sample of 240 breast cancer patients aged 30 to 73 years (Mean = 48.11, *SD* = 10.74) participated in this study. The following inclusion criteria were used to select the participants: (1) diagnosed breast cancer patients, (2) with age > 18 years, and (3) those who consented to participate in the study. The exclusion criteria were (1) patients with diagnosed psychiatric comorbidities and (2) patients with metastatic complications. The majority of the patient participants belonged to the Hindu community (82.9%), had high school education (28%) and were unemployed (61.2%). Most participants were married (82.1%) and lived with their families (99.6%). Some of the participants had a family history of cancer (16%). 18.6%, 32.1%, 27.8% and 21.5% of the participants diagnosed with stage 1, 2, 3, and 4 stages of cancer, respectively.

Measures

Below is a brief description of the self-report measures used in the study to assess motives, fear of cancer recurrence, optimism and

pessimism affecting resilience and QoL (psychological & social well-being) of breast cancer patients.

Unified Motive Scale (UMS - 3; Schonbrodt & Gerstenberg, 2012): The Unified Motive Scale measures power, achievement, affiliation, intimacy, and fear. The scale consists of 15 items. Two different item formats are present in the unified motive scale. Classical items are formulated as statements requiring an agreement rating and goals requiring an importance rating. Statements are rated on a 6-point Likert scale with ratings ranging from 1 (*Strongly Disagree*) to 6 (*Strongly Agree*). The goals are also rated on a 6-point Likert scale where each response option ranges from 1 (*Not important to me*) to 6 (*Extremely important to me*). The Cronbach's alpha of the subscales power, achievement, affiliation, intimacy and fear is .33, .65, .48, .64 and .73 in this study.

Fear of Cancer Recurrence Inventory (FCRI-SF; Simard & Savard, 2015): The fear of cancer recurrence inventory aims to understand the experience of worries about cancer recurrence. It is a nine-item questionnaire, which is a short form of the FCRI (42 items). The factors are triggers, severity, psychological distress, coping strategies, functioning impairments, insight and reassurance. The FCRI evaluates the presence and severity of intrusive thoughts associated with fear of cancer recurrence. The items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (*Not at all*) to 4 (*A great deal*). The Cronbach's alpha of the scale for cancer patients in this study is .91.

Life Orientation Test- R (Scheier et al., 1994): The life orientation scale is a 10-item measure of optimism versus pessimism. Of the ten items, three measure optimism, three measure pessimism, and four serve as fillers. Respondents rate each item on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (*Strongly Disagree*) to 4 (*Strongly Agree*). The Cronbach's alpha of the subscales' optimism and pessimism in this study is .70 and .46, respectively.

Bharathiar University Resilience Scale (Annalakshmi, 2009): Bharathiar University resilience scale is designed to assess the capacity of an individual to cope with stress and catastrophe and a characteristic of resistance to future negative events. The scale measures the duration taken to return to normalcy, reaction to negative events, response to risk factors (specifically unfavourable environment) in life, perception of the effect of past negative events, defining problems, hope/confidence in coping with future, and openness to experience and flexibility. In this research, a short version of BURS consisting of 10 items of the original scale was used. For all the items, 5-point scales were provided, ranging from 1 (*completely disagree*) to 5 (*agree*). The Cronbach's alpha of the scale for cancer patients is .83 in this study.

Quality of Life -Patient/ Cancer Survivor Version (Ferrel et al., 1995; 2012): Quality of Life Patient/cancer survivor version is a forty-one-item scale that measures the Quality of Life of a cancer patient. In this research, we used only 12 items selected through the lottery method, covering two dimensions: psychological and social well-being. The response options range from 0 (*no problem*) to 10 (*severe problem*). The Cronbach's alpha of the psychological well-being and social well-being subscales in this study are .75 and .84, respectively.

Procedure

Permission to conduct research on cancer patients was obtained from

three hospitals located in Coimbatore after the necessary permission and ethical committee clearance from Institutional Human Ethics Committee, PSG Institute of Medical Sciences and Research. The participants were recruited based on the information received from the hospitals using purposive sampling technique. The data were collected by visiting these hospitals' oncology departments. Before collecting data, written informed consent was obtained from breast cancer patients. Self-report measures were used to gather data from the participants. The measures were translated into vernacular language for better comprehension by the participants. The data collected from the participants were analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis.

Results

The results of multiple linear regression to examine predictors of the participants' resilience and quality of life are presented below.

Table 1

Motives Predicting Resilience among Breast Cancer Patients (N=240)

Variable	Unstd. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t
	B	SE	Beta	
Constant	25.73	2.95		8.72
Power	.35	.18	.14	1.97*
Achievement	.45	.18	.18	2.53 *
Affiliation	.01	.18	.01	0.08 ^{ns}
Intimacy	.45	.16	.18	2.81**
Fear	-.62	.13	-.32	-4.80 ***

Note. $R^2=.49$, Adj $R^2=.22$, $F(5,234) = 508.26$, *** $p<.001$, ** $p<.01$, * $p<.05$, ns= not sig

The multiple linear regression analysis for the predictor variable power, achievement, intimacy and fear produced $R^2=.49$, $F(5,234) = 508.26$, *** $p<.001$, ** $p<.01$, * $p<.05$. The analysis showed that power ($\beta = .14, p < .05$), achievement ($\beta = .18, p < .05$), and intimacy ($\beta = .18, p < .01$) positively predicted resilience while the dimension fear ($\beta = -.32, p < .001$) negatively predicted resilience among cancer patients. Affiliation does not significantly predict resilience among breast cancer patients.

Table 2

Fear of Cancer Recurrence Predicting Resilience among Breast Cancer Patients (N=240)

Variable	Unstd. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t
	B	SE	Beta	
Constant	40.60	.77		52.68
Fear of cancer recurrence	-.36	.05	-.43	-7.42***

Note. $R^2=.19$, Adj $R^2=.18$, $F(1,238) = 55.02$, *** $p<.001$

The simple linear regression analysis for the predictor variable fear of cancer recurrence produced $R^2=.19$, $F(1, 238) = 55.02$, *** $p<.001$. The analysis showed that fear of cancer recurrence ($\beta = -.43, p < .001$) negatively predicted resilience among breast cancer patients.

Table 3

Optimism and Pessimism Predicting Resilience among Breast Cancer Patients (N=240)

Variable	Unstd. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t
	B	SE	Beta	
Constant	17.91	1.83		9.78
Optimism	1.84	.16	.63	11.88***
Pessimism	.18	.18	.05	1.01 ^{ns}

Note. $R^2=.38$, Adj $R^2=.37$, $F(2,237)=72.27$, *** $p<.001$, ns= not sig

The multiple linear regression analysis for the predictor variable optimism produced $R^2=.38$, $F(2,237)=72.27$, *** $p<.001$. The analysis showed that Optimism ($\beta = .63$, $p < .001$) positively predicts resilience among breast cancer patients, while pessimism does not.

Table 4

Motives Predicting Psychological Well-being among Breast Cancer Patients (N=240)

Variable	Unstd. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t
	B	SE	Beta	
Constant	21.82	4.70		4.64 ^{ns}
Power	-.30	.28	-.07	-1.05 ^{ns}
Achievement	.36	.28	.09	1.26 ^{ns}
Affiliation	.22	.29	.05	.78 ^{ns}
Intimacy	1.31	.26	.32	5.13***
Fear	-1.03	.21	-.32	-5.03***

Note. $R^2=.32$, Adj $R^2=.31$, $F(5,233)=22.17$, *** $p<.001$, ns= not sig

The multiple linear regression analysis for the predictor variable intimacy and fear produced $R^2=.32$, $F(5,233)=22.17$, *** $p<.001$. The analysis showed that the dimension intimacy ($\beta = .32$, $p < .001$) positively predicted resilience, while the dimension fear ($\beta = -.32$, $p < .001$) negatively predicted resilience among breast cancer patients. Other dimensions of the unified motive scale do not significantly predict the psychological well-being dimension of QoL among breast cancer patients.

Table 5

Fear of Cancer Recurrence Predicting Psychological Well-being Dimension of QoL (N=240)

Variable	Unstd. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t
	β	SE	Beta	
Constant	47.33	1.12		42.14 ns
Fear of cancer recurrence	-.88	.07	-.63	-12.42***

Note. $R^2=.39$, Adj $R^2=.39$, $F(1,237)=154.31$, *** $p<.001$

The simple linear regression analysis for the predictor variable fear of cancer recurrence produced $R^2=.39$, $F(1,237)=154.31$, *** $p<.001$. The analysis showed that fear of cancer recurrence ($\beta = -.63$, $p < .001$) negatively predicted psychological well-being among cancer patients.

Table 6

Optimism and Pessimism Predicting Psychological Well-being Dimension of QoL (N=240)

Variable	Unstd. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t
	β	SE	Beta	
Constant	17.30	3.63		4.77
Optimism	1.89	.31	.38	6.15***
Pessimism	.14	.36	.02	0.39 ^{ns}

Note. $R^2=.14$, Adj $R^2=.13$, $F(2,236)=19.48$, *** $p<.001$, ns= not sig

The multiple linear regression analysis for predictor variable optimism produced $R^2=.14$, $F(2,236)=19.48$, *** $p<.001$. The analysis showed that optimism ($\beta = .38$, $p < .001$) positively predicts the psychological well-being dimension of QoL among breast cancer patients, while pessimism does not.

Table 7

Motives Predicting Social Well-being Dimension of QoL (N=240)

Variable	Unstd. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t
	β	SE	Beta	
Constant	25.02	4.94		5.07 ^{ns}
Power	.11	.29	.02	.36 ^{ns}
Achievement	-.14	.30	-.03	-.49 ^{ns}
Affiliation	.13	.30	.03	.45 ^{ns}
Intimacy	1.38	.27	.32	5.15***
Fear	-1.34	.22	-.39	-6.21***

Note. $R^2=.32$, Adj $R^2=.30$, $F(5,234)=21.87$, *** $p<.001$, ns= not sig

The multiple linear regression analysis for predictor variables intimacy and fear produced $R^2=.32$, $F(5,234)=21.87$, *** $p<.001$. The analysis showed that the dimension intimacy ($\beta = .32$, $p < .001$) positively predicted social well-being. In contrast, the dimension fear ($\beta = -.39$, $p < .001$) negatively predicted social well-being among cancer patients. Other dimensions of the unified motive scale do not significantly predict the social well-being dimension of QoL among breast cancer patients.

Table 8

Fear of Cancer Recurrence Predicting Social Well-being Dimension of QoL (N=240)

Variable	Unstd. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t
	β	SE	Beta	
Constant	47.84	1.02		46.94 ^{ns}
Fear of cancer recurrence	-1.09	.07	-.63	-16.87***

Note. $R^2=.55$, Adj $R^2=.54$, $F(1,238)=284.83$, *** $p<.001$

The simple linear regression analysis for the predictor variable fear of cancer recurrence produced $R^2=.55$, $F(1,238)=284.83$, *** $p<.001$. The analysis showed that fear of cancer ($\beta = -.63$, $p < .001$) negatively predicted the social well-being dimension of QoL among breast cancer patients.

Table 9

Optimism and Pessimism Predicting Social Well-being Dimension of QoL (N=240)

Variable	Unstd. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t
	β	SE	Beta	
Constant	16.22	3.89		4.17
Optimism	1.70	.33	.33	5.16***
Pessimism	.25	.38	.04	.65 ^{ns}

Note. $R^2=.10$, Adj $R^2=.10$, $F(2,237)=13.49$, *** $p<.001$, ns=not sig

The multiple linear regression analysis for predictor variable optimism produced $R^2=.10$, $F(2,237) = 13.49$, *** $p < .001$. The analysis showed that optimism ($\beta = .33$, $p < .001$) positively predicted the social well-being dimension of QoL among breast cancer patients, while pessimism did not.

Discussion

Regression analysis was carried out in the present study to examine whether motives, fear of cancer recurrence, optimism and pessimism predict resilience and QoL (psychological & social well-being) among breast cancer patients.

The results showed that the dimension 'power' of the unified motive scale positively predicted resilience. Breast cancer patients with more influence and control over their lives are likely to be more resilient. Patients are more likely to use proactive coping mechanisms, follow treatment guidelines, and keep a good attitude when they believe they have control over their everyday lives and treatment decisions. The concepts of empowerment and agency are intertwined. Giving people or groups the power to decide for themselves and take action to better their own lives and conditions is the process of empowerment. The agency describes a person's or a group's ability to act and make decisions on their own. A previous study has similarly found that psychological empowerment is linked to better mental health outcomes (Gillet et al., 2023). The two components of power motivation are a concern about having an impact on other people by influencing their attitudes, emotions, or behaviors and a concern about having status and prestige. Patients who believe they have the power to influence others may feel in charge of their own care and empowered to advocate for themselves. This sense of control can enhance their psychological strength, helping them cope with the difficulties of having cancer and aiding in their resilience.

The findings show that the dimension 'achievement' of the unified motive scale positively predicted resilience. The achievement motive is defined as a recurrent concern with a standard of excellence/fear of failure and the disposition to derive satisfaction from the mastery of challenging tasks (Schonbrodt, 2012). People with strong motivation for achievement are more likely to stick with their goals, change their tactics, and not give up when faced with difficulties (Duckworth et al., 2007). Resilience is significantly and positively impacted by an individual's capacity to combine cognitive, behavioral, and self-regulatory abilities to accomplish a goal (Ambarwulan & Haryanthi, 2016). Goal-oriented people typically have clear objectives and strive tirelessly toward them (Locke & Latham, 2002). Reaching those goals, no matter how small, can boost psychological resilience by giving a sense of progress and achievement.

Further, the present study results showed that the dimension

'intimacy' of the unified motive scale positively predicted resilience. In the unified motive scale, the intimacy motive is operationalized as a fear of losing emotional contact (Schonbrodt, 2012). People may seek out and keep safe attachments as a result of this fear, which is important for resilience. Secure attachments are crucial for resilience, according to attachment theory. Close relationships provide a sense of security for people to face challenges and explore the world (Bowlby, 1988). Patients feel understood and validated when they confide in close friends or family members, lessening feelings of isolation and despair. By acting as a psychological buffer, this emotional support helps patients in the resilience-building process and manage the stresses that come with receiving a cancer diagnosis and treatment.

The dimension 'fear' of the unified motive scale negatively predicted cancer patients' resilience, suggesting that a higher level of fear is associated with lower levels of resilience. Fear is a powerful emotional reaction to the perceived threat of cancer and its consequences, and it can make it more difficult for a person to manage the stress and difficulties that come with having cancer. The findings also indicated that fear of cancer recurrence negatively predicted resilience among breast cancer patients. Patients with breast cancer may experience intense dread because of the disease's high visibility and the potentially severe physical and psychological implications of its treatments, such as chemotherapy and mastectomy. Stress might be increased, and effective coping is impeded by the fear of recurrence and the long-term effects on body image and femininity. As a result, avoidance behaviors, stress, and a reduced capacity to use proactive coping strategies, which are critical for preserving resilience, can result from this elevated dread. Low psychological resilience seen in cancer survivors was found to be connected with a strong fear of cancer recurrence (Agac & Uzar-Ozdetin, 2022). Breast cancer survivors with high psychological resilience report feeling less fearful of their disease returning (Koral & Ciral, 2021). These results highlight how psychological resilience can be negatively impacted by a fear of cancer recurrence in breast cancer patients, highlighting the need to address this fear with increased resilience-building techniques.

'Optimism' positively predicted resilience among breast cancer patients in this study. This finding emphasizes the critical role that positive outlooks play in supporting psychological resilience in those coping with breast cancer. Optimism, which refers to having a positive and upbeat outlook on life's events, seems to be a powerful tool for helping breast cancer patients deal with their diagnosis and course of treatment. It supports people in keeping hope and concentrating on the good things that will happen, which is crucial for overcoming the challenges and uncertainties of cancer. Optimism provides the emotional and mental power to face the illness with courage and determination, strengthening resilience. This result is consistent with earlier studies showing the positive effects of optimism on psychological health and flexible coping mechanisms during difficult times (Carver et al., 2024; Scheier & Carver, 1985). Resilience lessens cancer symptoms and enhances overall functioning and health (Ruiz-Rodriguez et al., 2022).

The results illustrated that the dimension 'intimacy' of the unified motive scale positively predicted psychological well-being. The intimacy motivation, in the unified motive scale, is operationalized as the fear of losing emotional contact (Schonbrodt, 2012). This dread can motivate cancer patients to establish and maintain intimate relationships in an effort to protect their emotional

connections. These kinds of interactions usually take place in a few close relationships with significant others (Winter, 1991). Marital closeness strengthens the bond between spouses, enhances marital contentment, and subsequently enhances mental health (Hatami & Fadayi, 2015). A positive link was found between psychological well-being and marital intimacy (Aghamiri & Vaziri, 2019). Couples who view their partners as empathetic and readily available sources of support report feeling more secure and confident in themselves and experiencing better health and overall well-being (Han & Lee, 2017). This finding emphasizes how being close to others, having positive, profound interactions, practicing self-disclosure and warm mutual exchange (Sokolowski, 2008) is crucial for promoting people's psychological well-being.

The findings of the present study indicated that the dimension 'fear' of the unified motive scale negatively predicted psychological well-being among cancer patients, suggesting that a higher level of fear is associated with lower levels of psychological well-being. The analysis also showed that fear of cancer recurrence negatively predicted psychological well-being among cancer patients. Patients experience a significant burden both before and after treatment due to their fear of cancer recurrence (Mehta et al., 2003). Constant concern about a possible recurrence can make it more difficult for them to use adaptive coping mechanisms and keep a happy attitude. Consequently, this chronic fear may weaken the psychological strength needed to navigate the challenges of cancer treatment and recovery, thereby diminishing psychological well-being. A study revealed that general health and mental well-being significantly predict the fear of cancer recurrence (Mehta et al., 2003).

'Optimism' positively predicted psychological well-being in the present study. Optimism plays a significant role in enhancing psychological well-being. The effects of optimism are always good, and the effects of pessimism are always bad (Carver & Scheier, 1985; Scheier & Carver, 2010). A study shows that optimism and psychological well-being were positively correlated among teenagers (Parveen et al., 2016). Also, optimism is positively correlated with psychological well-being in the general public and people with medical conditions (Scheier & Carver, 1992). Cancer patients tended to have good subjective well-being when they had high optimism and spiritual well-being (Werdani, 2022). Optimistic individuals are more likely to employ effective coping strategies when facing challenges. These adaptive coping mechanisms contribute to better psychological well-being. Resilience impacts psychological well-being, but no matter how resilient a person is, optimism might help them feel more balanced (Souri, 2013).

The study findings demonstrated that the dimension 'intimacy' of the unified motive scale, that is, the fear of losing emotional contact (Schonbrodt, 2012) positively predicted social well-being. There are limited studies on the relationship between social well-being, intimacy, fear, and fear of cancer recurrence among breast cancer patients. Social well-being refers to a person's level of satisfaction with the quality of their interpersonal interactions (Kraemer et al., 2011). Patients with cancer who value closeness above everything else and are afraid of losing that emotional connection may actively look for and keep up encouraging interactions with peers, family, and friends. This implies that those who strongly desire to maintain intimate emotional ties are likely to put in more effort to build and maintain those relationships. Investing in social relationships can increase social support, an essential aspect of social well-being.

The research findings pointed out that the dimension 'fear' of the

unified motive scale negatively predicted social well-being among cancer patients, suggesting that higher fear is associated with lower levels of social well-being. The results also showed that fear of cancer recurrence negatively predicted social well-being. Patients who experience fear of cancer recurrence may experience emotional distress and are likely to withdraw from social interactions. It lessens interactions with others, leading to lower social well-being levels. We also find that optimism positively predicts social well-being. The degree to which a person anticipates having pleasant experiences in the future is known as optimism (Scheier & Carver, 1985). Optimists tend to have greater overall social support (Park & Folkman, 1997). This positive perspective can promote proactive social activity involvement and strengthen interpersonal bonds. As a result, increased optimism fosters a social support system, which improves social well-being. Social support can also assist people in focusing on the advantages and potential benefits that could come from a challenging circumstance (Pearlin & Schooler, 1978) and is therefore connected to optimism.

Conclusion

This study clarifies the complex interplay among motivational factors, fear of cancer recurrence, optimism, psychological resilience and dimensions of QoL in breast cancer patients. It is observed that power, achievement, and intimacy motives stand out as important predictors of resilience, indicating that sentiments of personal empowerment, a success orientation, and strong interpersonal ties are essential for building resilience in the face of adversity. Furthermore, optimism is shown to be a strong predictor of resilience, highlighting the need to retain a hopeful mindset in the face of the difficulties associated with a cancer diagnosis and course of treatment. In addition, the study also shows how worry, fear in general and fear of cancer in particular, negatively affect patients' ability to bounce back. This emphasizes the importance of providing therapies that target and manage fear to increase patients' resilience and ability to adapt. Also, psychological and social well-being among cancer patients is considerably enhanced by strong interpersonal relationships and an optimistic outlook. On the other hand, fear, both generalized and cancer-specific, appears to have an adverse effect on psychological and social well-being. These findings highlight how critical it is to cultivate support networks, hold onto optimism, and deal with fears to assist cancer patients' overall quality of life.

While discussing the limitations of the study, it is important to note that the participants were chosen from three hospitals in Coimbatore and were all under treatment at the time of recruitment. Despite efforts to ensure proper representation within this particular context, it is possible that the findings will not apply to a larger community of breast cancer patients who might receive different therapies and have access to a variety of healthcare facilities. The self-reported data used in this study have the risk of response biases and social desirability effects. Furthermore, it is important to recognize that the study may not have accounted for all potential factors that could have affected breast cancer patients. Factors such as comorbidities, duration of cancer, or specific treatment regimens were not explicitly included as covariates in the analyses. These unaccounted cancer-related factors could contribute to the outcome variance beyond the measured factors.

Clinical interventions that recognize and address aspects of cancer patients' lives like "power," "achievement," and "intimacy" may

strengthen their resilience and help them deal with the challenges in life. The recognition of the negative effects of fear, specifically cancer-related dread, on cancer patients' resilience highlights the significance of incorporating techniques for managing fear into support initiatives. Providing patients with individualized coping strategies and resources for fear reduction may increase their resilience. Interventions that promote positive thinking and those that aim at fostering meaningful connections may contribute to the psychological well-being of cancer patients. Extensive research on the mechanisms that underlie the associations between these dimensions and their effects on the prognosis of cancer patients may yield insightful findings.

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